

ART3mis: Ray-based textual annotation on 3D cultural objects

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Extended abstract

As 3D objects are progressively becoming pervasive in archaeology and cultural heritage applications, enhanced functionalities surpassing the simplistic 3D visualisation are required all the more. Among the first and most fundamental such requirements is the attachment of metadata on top of the 3D representation of the cultural objects and the capability of a multi-layered representation. To be able to provide such rich environments for visualisation and study, those systems need to be complemented or coupled with what is called annotation functionalities.

3D object annotation is the process of selecting a region over a 3D surface and linking that region to a high-level representation either in structured or in free form. Annotation on 3D objects is typically considered in two forms, either as an automated feature or semantics-based region segmentation (Nousias et al. 2020) or as a manually (or in some cases computer assisted) selected region characterization (Arnaoutoglou et al. 2003). While the former form relates to automated semantics extraction for various computer vision and graphics applications, the latter is most suited to cultural heritage applications, like conservation. In this scenario, 3D objects are presented to experts, which are called to annotate either the various degradation effects on a reconstructed object's surface, or any restoration processes that took place (Ponchio et al. 2020).

Since there has been no standardization in this field, each project and research team typically comes up with a new idea, method and approach to implement an annotation tool that is usually domain or even problem-specific. There is also no standardization to how the annotations are stored, that is, how the metadata are to be recorded, thus having today a multitude of approaches and solutions. Among the most challenging issues in implementing a 3D annotation system are (a) the GUI design, (b) the input conversion and association, (c) the management of high-res data, (d) the representation schemes, (e) the annotation format and data handling, and (f) the annotation as a web application (Ponchio et al. 2020).

Methodologically, annotations can be attached either to single points, lines, voxels, or regions on a 3D object's surface. In addition, annotation regions can be defined (a) on the surface of the objects, as collections of polygons, (b) on the texture of the objects, in UV-space, apparently leading to a 2D annotation approach and (c) on a hybrid space, fusing annotation on 2D images with reprojection techniques to transfer the annotations in 3D space.

This paper presents ART3mis, a user-friendly interactive textual annotation tool for 3D cultural objects, which is primarily focusing on heritage conservators. The idea originated in the EU project WARMEST¹ where an annotation tool was needed for the conservators to annotate the degradation on the 3D models of the columns in the Patio de los Leones in the

¹ Project WARMEST website @ <https://warmestproject.eu>.

UNESCO World Heritage Site of Alhambra, Granada, Spain. As the tool was required for scientific use by experts with no technical skills in 3D imaging and graphics, the tool had to follow the intuitive WYSIWYG design and be able to handle the various 3D models available from the 3D digitization that was applied in real time. Image-based digitization was employed, and highly detailed 3D replicas had been created, thus models of high polygon counts need to be handled in real time.

ART3mis is using the direct-on-surface annotation approach, by providing various ways of selecting a region of interest on an object's 3D model surface. It should be noted that ART3mis works on the textured 3D model, which is a method that has been largely discussed in the relevant literature as the most appropriate, as in many cases the texture assists in a more accurate identification of defects or degradations on materials for conservation applications. In addition, ART3mis supports not only the one-time annotation but also the processing of previous annotations, consisting a complete annotation management tool. The annotation storage strategy selected in this case was that of a json structured text file, which is a technique that becomes pervasive in today's Web-connected systems.

Figure 1. Selection of region with 'lasso' and addition of a second region with 'brush'.

ART3mis includes a typical 3D model viewing interface that supports multiple region selections on a single 3D object. Selection (see Figure 1) can be done by either (a) using a typical lasso technique (as in many 2D imaging software), which enables the selection of any region of interest on top of an object's surface, or (b) using a brush technique (user-defined brush size), which enables the 'painting' of a region of interest. Multiple regions can be selected in this way, color-coded and connected with textual annotations, all stored in json format for future use.

Currently, ART3mis supports OBJ (with accompanying MTL, JPG, etc.) files for textured 3D models and saves the annotations in JSON format. It is limited to the Windows platform and is not yet converted to a cross-platform Web-based application.

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Bibliography

- Arnautoglou, F, V Evagelidis, G Pavlidis, N Tsirliganis, and C Chamzas. 2003. “3D-GIS: New Ways in Digitization and Visualization of Cultural Objects.” In *Workshop on the Digitization of Cultural Content*, 27:28.
- Nousias, S., G. Arvanitis, A. S. Lalos, G. Pavlidis, C. Koulamas, A. Kalogeras, and K. Moustakas. 2020. “A Saliency Aware CNN-Based 3D Model Simplification and Compression Framework for Remote Inspection of Heritage Sites.” *IEEE Access* 8: 169982–1. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3023167>.
- Ponchio, Federico, Marco Callieri, Matteo Dellepiane, and Roberto Scopigno. 2020. “Effective Annotations over 3D Models.” In *Computer Graphics Forum*, 39:89–105. Wiley Online Library.